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Abstract

The scientific vision of E-RIHS unfolds around a solid core, in which Excellence and Innovation coexist and convolute towards the evolution of E-RIHS itself and more generally of the Heritage Science domain. The E-RIHS scientific strategy is stepping upon open access to scientific information, both publications and data, with the ambition to contribute efficiently to a new era in Heritage Science. Prerequisite and cornerstone in the perspective of Open Heritage Science is the knowledge of existing rules and tools and proper management of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). This document includes a summary of resources on IPR concepts, existing rules and legal definitions and goes into the specificities of IPRs in the field of Heritage Science, including Heritage Science data. It analyses the different issues that can arise from working on Heritage Objects and how E-RIHS can address them. The document provides a first overview of E-RIHS ERIC IPR strategy with respect to E-RIHS members' national policies.

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Abstract (for dissemination)	This deliverable analyses the core concepts of IPR related to Heritage Science and provides detailed good IPR management practices to be implemented in E-RIHS ERIC.
Keywords	Intellectual Property (IP), Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), Intellectual Property Management (IPM), Practices , Concepts, Legal issues, Policies, Access

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Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
HS	Heritage Science
IP	Intellectual Property
IPM	Intellectual Property Management
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
TNA	Trans-National Access
TRIP	Trade-Related aspects of Intellectual Property rights
TT	Technology Transfer
TTO	Technology Transfer Office
WIPO	World Intellectual Property Organization
WTO	World Trade Organization
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

Narrative (technical) description

I. Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). Protection but not without risks

1. IPR provide a protection for any kind of intellectual work

General definition of IPR, main categories (industrial/ copyrights)

According to the WIPO (World Intellectual Property Organization), **Intellectual Property (IP)** refers to **creations of the mind**: inventions; literary and artistic works and symbols, names and images used in commerce¹.

The importance of protecting intellectual property was first recognized in the Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property in 1883 and the Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works in 1886. Both treaties are currently administered by the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO).

Furthermore, different countries have established legal and regulatory frameworks to protect IP for two main reasons. One is to provide a statutory expression a) to the moral and economic rights of creators on their creations and b) to the rights of the public in accessing those creations. The second is to promote creativity and innovation as well as the dissemination and application of its results, and to encourage fair trade, which would contribute to economic and social development².

Intellectual property is a term that describes a number of distinct types of intangible assets. The protection of IP allows a rights' holder to exclude others from interfering with or allowing the use property right only in specified ways. There exist various types of IP protection and each one is different, varying in the subject matter that can be covered, the time frame of protection, and total cost of implementation. Although some inventions may be covered by multiple types of IP protection, it is important to consider a number of business and legal factors before selecting an optimum protection strategy. Some technologies require strong IP protection to commercialize, but unnecessary costs can derail bringing a product to market. IP departments of organizations weigh these various considerations and perform essential IP protection functions. This primer introduces researchers to the main forms of IP and its legal aspects³.

Intellectual property is usually divided into two branches, namely **copyright and industrial property**.

Copyright relates to intellectual work or artistic creations (poems, novels, music, paintings, cinematographic works etc). In most European languages other than English, copyright is known as **author's rights**. The term copyright refers to the main act which, in respect of literary and artistic creations, may be made only by the author or with his/her authorization. That act is the making of copies of the literary or artistic work, such as a book, a painting, a sculpture, a photograph, or a motion picture. The second term, author's rights, refers to the person who is the creator of the artistic work, its author, thus underlining the fact, recognized in most laws, that the author has certain specific rights in his creation, such as the right to prevent a distorted reproduction, which only he/she can exercise, whereas other rights, such as the right to make copies, can be exercised by other persons, for example, a publisher who has obtained a license to this effect from the author.

Industrial property takes a range of forms. These include patents to protect scientific or technological inventions and industrial designs, which are aesthetic creations determining the appearance of industrial products. Industrial property also covers trademarks, service marks, layout-designs of integrated circuits, commercial names and designations, as well as geographical indications, and protection against unfair competition. In some of these, the aspect of intellectual creation, although existent, is less clearly defined. What counts here is that the object of industrial property typically consists of signs transmitting information, in particular to consumers, as regards

products and services offered on the market. Protection is directed against unauthorized use of such signs likely to mislead consumers, and against misleading practices in general,^[2].

As set out in the Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property (Article 1 (3)), “Industrial property shall be understood in the broadest sense and shall apply not only to industry and commerce proper, but likewise to agricultural and extractive industries and to all manufactured or natural products, for example, wines, grain, tobacco leaf, fruit, cattle, minerals, mineral waters, beer, flowers, and flour.”

2. IPR can take many useful forms

Issues of IP should be clarified and ruled at management level and respective measures protecting IP should constitute an integral component of any management of knowledge plan in order to ensure the optimal use and exploitation of research outcomes. In fact, it is critically important to identify the relevant IP that were created before, during, outside and after the collaboration time frame. These can be classified as background, foreground, or sideground IP defined below.

Background IP: Intellectual property specially listed as pre-existing one and excluded from the beginning;

Foreground IP: Joint intellectual property – each joint owner has unlimited right to use, grant and assign licenses without the need for accounting or compensation to co-owners;

Very often a collaboration partner requires more specific rights than just the foreground intellectual property that is created during a collaboration. Common but important issues in this respect include allocation of ownership of IP, generated in the framework of a project (“foreground”), identification of IP possessed by the parties before starting the project (“background”) and which of this is necessary for carrying out the work planned for the project or needed for exploitation purposes, access rights to foreground and background in relation to exploitation and the sharing of revenues. In a collaborative research project, ownership of the foreground should stay with the party that has generated it, but can be allocated to different parties on the basis of a contractual agreement concluded in advance, adequately reflecting the parties' respective interests, tasks and financial or other contributions to the project⁴.

Sideground IP: Results, including information, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in parallel to the project.

As stated by M. Bader⁵ “Sideground intellectual property developed during the collaboration period, but in not-project-related activities, should be classified according to the form in which it will be used in the future”. It can also be divided into confidential and non-confidential sideground IP. Difficulties obviously occur only if the IP is regarded as confidential. It might be used internally in research or exploratory activities, or externally within other projects.

3. International, European and National legal frameworks

Intellectual property rights are like any other property right. They allow creators, or owners, of patents, trademarks or copyrighted works to benefit from their own work or investment in a creation. These rights are outlined in Article 27 of the Universal **Declaration of Human Rights**, which provides for the right of one to benefit via the protection of moral and material interests resulting from authorship of scientific, literary or artistic productions. Intellectual property, very broadly, encompasses the legal rights which result from intellectual activity in the industrial, scientific, literary and artistic fields.

The importance of IP was first recognized in the **Paris Convention** for the Protection of Industrial Property (1883) and the **Berne Convention** for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works (1886) provided for the establishment of an "International Bureau". The two bureaus were united in 1893 and, in 1970, were replaced by the World Intellectual Property Organization, by virtue of the WIPO Convention (The WIPO Convention, the constituent instrument of the **World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO)**, [1], was signed at Stockholm on July 14, 1967, entered into force in 1970 and was amended in 1979). WIPO is an intergovernmental organization, with its headquarters in Geneva, Switzerland⁶ and a mandate from its signatories to promote the protection of IP throughout the world through cooperation among countries and in collaboration with other international organizations. In 1974 it became one of the specialized agencies within the United Nations system. Under **the Paris Convention**, the national treatment principle allowed for what was usually called the "asymmetries", i.e., the adoption of different standards of protection by different countries in accordance with different levels of national development (provided national treatment was secured). The TRIPS (**Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights**) Agreement of the World Trade Organization (WTO) established minimum standards of protection that each government has to give to the IP of fellow WTO members, thus limiting the former scope for flexible national approaches.

There are three levels of legal frameworks that are relevant to IPR in the European Union: national, EU, and international. In some respect these are converging but notable differences still remain that often generate ambiguities and difficulties in protecting and exploiting IP.

National laws involve the legislature of an individual state. Each European Union (EU) Member State has national authorities that address IPR laws in it. Although, in some cases, it is the EU as a whole that has the authority to regulate IPR, national offices in many Member States often provide registration services and information to protect IPR. As noted in I.1 different states have legal and regulatory frameworks to protect IP for two main reasons. One is to provide a statutory expression as regards a) the moral and economic rights of creators on their creations and b) the rights of the public in accessing those creations. The second is to promote creativity and innovation as well as the dissemination and application of its results, and to encourage fair trade, which would contribute to economic and social development,^[2].

The **European Commission** (EC) has been working towards harmonising laws relating to IPR in EU countries in order to lower barriers to trade and to create efficient EU-wide systems for the protection of such rights. It fights against piracy and counterfeiting and aims to help businesses, especially small businesses, access and use intellectual property rights more effectively⁷. The **EU law** is the "supra-national law" in effect across the European Union. In addition to EU treaties, the EU also adopts Regulations and Directives. Regulations these are automatically binding on Member States and leave less flexibility. Directives allow Member States to determine the means of attaining that result as they normally permit some discretion as to the exact rules to be adopted.

The impetus of certain international instruments dealing with IP – such as the Agreement on the Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPs Agreement) of the World Trade Organization (WTO) and the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) Copyright Treaty and the WIPO Performances and Phonograms Treaty – has generated a vast amount of activity in drafting new national copyright laws or revising existing ones.

A number of relevant Directives are listed below, which have been or are being adopted by various states as a reference framework for (re)defining their national copyright laws.

On **December 21, 1988**, the Council of the European Union adopted the 1st Directive to Approximate the Laws of the Member States Relating to Trade Marks (No. 89/104/EEC, repealed by EU Directive 2008/95/EC). This Directive deals, among other matters, with the signs which can

constitute a mark, grounds for refusal or invalidity, including conflicts with other rights, sanctions for non-use and grounds for revocation.

On **October 13, 1998**, the European Parliament and the Council of the European Union adopted the Directive on the Legal Protection of Designs. The Directive defines, for instance, the terms “designs,” “product” and “complex product.” (Directive 98/71/EC)

The EC **Directive 96/9/EC** of 11 March 1996⁸ on the legal protection of databases considers both copyright and sui generis right in order to protect the databases. Article 3.1 provides that “*databases which, by reason of the selection or arrangement of their contents, constitute the author’s own intellectual creation shall be protected as such by copyright*”.

The EC **Directive 98/44** on the Legal Protection of Biotechnological Inventions, for instance, which entered into force on July 30, 1998, harmonized the rules concerning patent protection for biotechnological inventions.

At European Union level Copyright is governed by the Directive **2001/29/EC**⁹, whereas the Database protection is governed by Directive 96/9/EC.

The **Directive 2001/29/EC** of 22 May 2001 on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society, also known as the InfoSoc Directive¹⁰ (Information Society Directive), implements the WIPO Copyright Treaty and harmonises the aspects of copyright law across Europe.

Finally, the **Directive (EU) 2019/790** of 17 April 2019 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market and amending the aforementioned Directives 96/9/EC and 2001/29/EC provided a much-anticipated modernization of the EU regulatory framework in a world where the use of protected material is increasingly digital and cross border. It harmonizes rules on licensing practices and access to content and provides measures to improve the functioning of the copyright market especially its digital component. This directive creates important exceptions for both scientific research and for cultural heritage institutions. These two terms, as defined in Article 2 of the Directive, should cover most (if not all) the members of E-RIHS. This text must be implemented by the EU Members States before July 2021, i.e. before the creation of E-RIHS ERIC.

Furthermore, **International treaties** that are relevant to IP protection are effectively those maintained by the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), which aim to promote the effective use and protection of IP worldwide. The WIPO Convention established WIPO in 1967 with a mandate from its signatories to promote the protection of IP throughout the world through cooperation among countries and in collaboration with other international organizations. The WIPO headquarters are in Geneva, Switzerland, [6].

At present, there is no single framework for copyright law in Europe that is valid across all countries on the continent. Instead, each country has its own set of copyright laws, which are backed up by the help of international copyright agreements and EU legislation. Copyright, in particular, can be a powerful catalyst within national economies¹¹. “Copyright” and “authors’ rights” take very different approaches to authors and their social role. Seen historically over its long development, copyright has focused on the audience. Authors rights in contrast have targeted creators and their claims to ensure the authenticity of their works. Copyright encourages innovation and promotes dissemination. Authors rights restrain distribution inhibiting public exposure. Authors rights speak for creators while copyright favours the audience¹². The French legislation on authors’ rights, personified by the use of the ‘*droit d’auteur*’ concept, is the most protective one for authors in the EU. In the French tradition, authors’ rights are personal rights, to be discussed on the level of human rights. By contrast, the Anglo-Saxon tradition conceives ‘copyright’ as an economic right. The United Kingdom (UK) 1988 Copyright Designs and Patents Act states that ‘copyright is a property right’. With the exception of the UK and Ireland, all other EU states have copyright legislation, where moral

rights – the right for authors to protect their good name, their reputation and their works – are central¹³.

4. The risks of IPR mismanagement

Over the past decade, IP has become widely perceived as an important economic asset, whose value can be enhanced by proactive and strategic policies.¹⁴ Today, even technology start-up and spin-off companies have started commercializing innovations and existing technologies¹⁵.

The IPR process is a sequence of activities through which research structures companies or individuals maintain and exploit their patents, designs, trademarks, copyrights, and trade secrets. Activities involved in this process can be as simple as obtaining IP rights and keeping them renewed or as complicated as developing an integrated IP strategy and aligning it with business strategies. To this end, managing IP and doing it efficiently is clearly very important as this will ensure that IP is exploited to its fullest extent and serves to maximize profitability or other business-related opportunities.

Thus the main objective of *intellectual property management* (IPM) and technology transfer is to assist in the utilization and commercialization of economically valuable novel IPRs connected with research results into trade and industry¹⁶. D. Modic and N. Damij (2018) state that “Maximizing the value from innovation, in particular through intellectual property rights (IPR), is a key element of intellectual property rights management (IPRM)”¹⁷. Intellectual property is a crucial contributor for knowledge economy and generates monopoly position in return for providing payoffs to innovation. A proper IPM plan aims at establishing protection of IP, leveraging IP into the market and eventually producing revenue. It also helps organizations to evaluate their patent portfolios¹⁸.

Managing IPR will thus have at least two dimensions on the level of individual processes: one is the legal-administrative dimension, the other a business dimension (combined with a strategic dimension), [17]. Hence, IPR management means managing the so-called Back-office side of it (legal and administrative) as well as the so-called Front-office processes. The latter are concerned with how IPRs can be beneficial for a business (and is highly connected to the strategic dimension). These two expressions were also used recently in a report by CPA Global (2014) and are mostly recognized by the IP executives across the world¹⁹.

In general, following good IPR practices is a path that satisfies a) Institutions b) rights holders, c) users and d) potential consumers. Rights issues need to be handled at an organizational level. Usually, a good IPR management scenario for projects follows three steps a) determining risks b) developing an IPR strategy that takes into account dissemination of information and open science principles c) drafting agreements and policies that enable strategic IPR management including Digital rights management. The strategy should be evaluated, weighing first the risk factors. The most commonly examined risk factors are: market risk, technical risk, economic risk and management/human resources risk etc.

A review of the literature suggests that a well-constructed approach for protecting and managing IP is fundamental to extract its full value and to create an intangible asset portfolio. Hence, a structured, systematic handling of both innovation strategy and IP protection (as the legal reflection of innovation) tends to lower the level of uncertainty, and managing risks is strongly ingrained in IPR management, [17].

In the context of **research organizations** a proactive IP policy may generate additional revenues, but this definitely is not the sole objective. It can support their mission of generating socio-economic benefits, and can become a key element to attract students, young researchers, competitive scientists and further research funding, in particular from the private sector and at international

level. The dissemination and exploitation of research results should be steadily promoted as broadly as possible, including policies supporting open access publication²⁰.

At the European level, a number of policies are already in place to support the development of Open Science, including open access guidelines and the set-up of the European Open Science Cloud. The adoption of Open Science principles is necessary in order to ensure the best use and greatest impact of the investments put into research and innovation in Europe²¹. On July 17, 2012, the European Commission published its Communication to the European Parliament and the Council entitled '*Towards better access to scientific information: Boosting the benefits of public investments in research*' (Brussels, 17.7.2012 COM(2012) 401²². The current approach of the EC, consists of asking researchers to make their data as open as possible and as closed as necessary.

It is noted that according to Crouzier (2007) there are no incompatibilities between IPR and Open Science. On the contrary the IPR framework, if correctly defined from the onset, becomes an essential tool to regulate open science and ensure that the efforts from different contributors are correctly rewarded. Their definition is depending on the objective of the research, The European Commission has a role in promoting open science and its balance with IPR. This is especially important at a time when policy on copyright and definition are being redefined and the Open Science Cloud is being established. These new policies will build the framework for the leadership of Europe in Open Science, [21]. Likewise, Principles and Guidelines (such as the OECD Principles and Guidelines for Access to Research Data from Public Funding) improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the global science system. They are not intended to hinder its development with onerous obligations and regulations or impose new costs on national science systems²³.

II. IPR management of Heritage Science: between Heritage and Open Science

1. Heritage management and IPR strategies

The relationship between Heritage and IPR is very complex, has significant local and national variations, and involves institutions and actors with divergent interests. As concluded by M. Burri in a chapter of *The Oxford Handbook of International Cultural Heritage Law*, “although intellectual property law has developed sophisticated rules with regard to a variety of intellectual property forms, it is based on certain author-centered and mercantilist premises that do not work so well with the protection of traditional knowledge and traditional cultural expressions. The sources, the dynamics and the embeddedness of cultural heritage cannot be adequately matched by a set of economic rights. Expressions of cultural heritage “fail” the legal tests in IP law precisely because of some of their intrinsic characteristics – because they have been passed from generation to generation, belong to the community, or cannot be separated from land or religion”²⁴.

This complexity increases in some of the fields of tangible cultural heritage conservation and management, especially when the ownership cannot be clearly traced from the start. This can be the case for tangible cultural heritage with traceable chain of ownership, which is common in fields such as archaeology. G. P. Nicholas and K. P. Bannister²⁵ point out that “a central question raised by consideration of intellectual property rights is whose property these products [tangible cultural heritage] are and how they are protected”. The observable lack of this consideration concerning these issues by Heritage Scientists may lead to problems related to:

- a) publication and ownership of copyright in books, reports, and articles,
- b) access to, public disclosure of, and ownership of copyright in photographs of artefacts,
- c) fiduciary duties related to the secrecy of sacred sites, which could also include copyright in maps,

- d) ownership, secrecy, and publication of traditional knowledge that may result from archaeological research, and
- e) ownership of, copyright, or trademarks related to the artefacts, designs, or marks uncovered during archaeological research”, [25].

As highlighted by works realised by the CARARE network²⁶ and the Kennisland think tank²⁷, “all cultural works are in the public domain except from the limited time period when they are restricted by Intellectual Property Rights”. As explained before, the duration and the extent of this protection remain different among countries despite the efforts towards harmonisation at the European level.

Building upon these findings and on the experience of the members of E-RIHS, we therefore recommend for E-RIHS:

- to avoid engaging in ownership related inquiries. This must be clearly stated and formally accepted by all Heritage Scientists involved in the E-RIHS activities. It should also refrain from engaging into direct authentication requests, but without hampering the use of its scientific results by the Heritage Science community in authentication studies.
- to ensure that users formally declare their rights on the studied object(s) and that they are allowed to work on it (them). Users must also be liable for the insurance of the object(s) studied.
- As a general rule, a formal agreement must be reached between either the ERIC or its providers and the users concerning the repartition of IPR and the associated risks. This agreement should establish that neither the ERIC nor the provider is liable for any issue raising from a breach of IPR from the part of the users.

2. Heritage Science creates scientific data about Heritage Objects

The notion of cultural or natural heritage has evolved considerably to encompass, in its broadest sense, cultural expressions and traditional knowledge *“The body of all natural or man-made goods, with no limit as to time or place”*²⁸.

The 2003 UNESCO Convention ultimately subscribed to a broad definition and intangible cultural heritage which is said to encompass “the practices, representations, expressions, knowledge, skills – as well as the instruments, objects, artefacts and cultural spaces associated therewith – that communities, groups and, in some cases, individuals recognize as part of their cultural heritage”²⁹. The cultural heritage of a community or nation lies at the heart of its identity and links its past with its present and future. Cultural heritage is also “living” – it is constantly recreated as traditional artists and practitioners bring fresh perspectives and experiences to their work³⁰.

Notably, as long as 3,000 years ago, Bronze age Aegean craftsmen used to engrave, stamp or paint their marks on the containers of their products (oil or wine) before sending them to the harbours of the Mediterranean area in order to secure the quality and the trademark. Their practice slowly evolved into the modern development of model contracts, codes of conduct and guidelines for use by cultural heritage archives, museums and other institutions, helps these organizations in managing the IP aspects of their cultural heritage collections.

The term cultural heritage encompasses two main concepts of heritage:

- a. movable cultural heritage (paintings, sculptures, coins, manuscripts), immovable cultural heritage (monuments, archaeological sites, and so on) underwater cultural heritage (shipwrecks, underwater ruins and cities)
- b. Intangible cultural heritage: oral traditions, performing arts, rituals etc.

The recognition of “intangible cultural heritage” and the need for its preservation have been among the key, although relatively recent, developments in international heritage law as described by J. Blake, in his work titled ‘Preliminary Study into the Advisability of Developing a New Standard-setting Instrument for the Safeguarding of Intangible Cultural Heritage’ (“Traditional Culture and Folklore”)³¹. The 2003 Convention ultimately subscribed to a broad definition and intangible cultural heritage is said to encompass “the practices, representations, expressions, knowledge, skills – as well as the instruments, objects, artefacts and cultural spaces associated therewith – that communities, groups and, in some cases, individuals recognize as part of their cultural heritage”, [29].

Cultural institutions, including museums, libraries and archives, play an invaluable role in the preservation, safeguarding and promotion of collections of cultural objects, such as artifacts, photographs, sound recordings, designs films, manuscripts etc. The advent of the information technologies, with easy digitization and dissemination via the Internet has compelled museums to keep up with technical and social changes such as the surge of mobile media, of big data, of community’s networks and has offered them the possibility to leverage these new means to carry on their mandates³².

Cultural heritage objects, such as artifacts, paintings, petroglyphs, folklore and traditional knowledge, can be copied, patented, and trademarked. Usually identified are the following types of copyright-protected assets that were either held by or owned by museums as part of their collections: a) Photographic images of artifacts and artworks in museum collections; b) Audio recordings and publications, such as CDs; c) Audio-visual works; d) Multimedia productions whether on CD or available on the Internet; e) Publications, and educational material, whether in print or electronic; and f) Databases of information about collections³³

Intellectual property, in particular copyright, is highly valuable to the development of a forward thinking society. Modern history has shown that culture, and in particular the enrichment of a society’s heritage, is dependent upon adequate IP protection provided to literary and artistic works. Cultural heritage is the legacy of physical artifacts and intangible attributes of a group or society that are inherited from past generations, maintained in the present and bestowed for the benefit of future generations. Both cultural heritage and IP are creations of the mind that have economic value, being species of property³⁴. Cultural rights and IPR are both recognized as human rights in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948). The relationship between culture and copyright has been described in an excellent article by G. Nicholas and K Bannister (2004)²⁵.

It is often stated that the principal goal of IP laws is to ensure that information enters the public domain in a timely fashion while allowing creators, be they individuals or corporate groups, to derive reasonable financial and social benefits from their work. Once a work enters the public domain, it loses most protections³⁵. Does actually intellectual property protection have a limited time span after which the intellectual property becomes part of the public domain? Does the masterpiece of “Mona Lisa,” belong to the public domain? It is owned by the Louvre and may not be entirely in the public domain in a copyright sense. The museum controls access to it and access to quality reproductions. For example, paintings that hang on the walls of public museums may be freely accessible and reproduction by means of photography may be permitted, but it does not mean that the paintings are in the public domain. Likewise, being able to view a reproduction of a work, or artifact, on the Internet does not mean that the work is in the public domain. The public domain, in the context of the IP law, is generally said to consist of intangible materials that are not subject to exclusive IPR and which are, therefore, freely available to be used or exploited by any person. Contrary to some perceptions, material is not in the public domain simply because it is accessible or available through a free and open source³⁶.

The digital revolution has dramatically increased the ability of individuals and corporations to appropriate and profit from the cultural knowledge, which is largely unprotected by existing IP law. In response, legal scholars, anthropologists, activists now propose new legal regimes designed to defend cultures by radically expanding the notion of copyright.

The great value and significance of digital heritage was affirmed by two UNESCO documents released in 2003: the Guidelines for the Preservation of Digital Heritage (National Library of Australia 2003)³⁷ and the Charter on the Preservation of the Digital Heritage (UNESCO 2009)³⁸. In fact, digital heritage shares some common characteristics with cultural heritage. The digital heritage research is centered on the techniques and knowledge for (1) digitalization of the heritage ontology; (2) preservation of digital heritage; (3) the use of digital heritage (4) demonstration, sharing, and publicity of digital heritage; and (5) laws and regulations on digital heritage protection³⁹.

In the framework of E-RIHS, the scientific study of cultural artefacts, consists in a fundamental interdisciplinary research. It fosters the use of highly sophisticated analysis techniques and high precision instruments to avail a better reading of artefacts and artworks and a deeper understanding of their physical composition, dating, conservation and materials. In the same framework, finding existing data, accessing them through a set of services, providing them with Interoperable formats, and Reusing them in new analyses opens new perspectives for the community working on Cultural Heritage. Organising all the data about an artefact and making them available to the community of researchers would indeed give “new life” to data otherwise forgotten after a paper publication, allowing for new analyses on already acquired data to address different problems without repeating the measurement⁴⁰.

At present, several European organisations and EC funded projects in the cultural heritage domain, are working together to set up principles and mechanisms for improving the use and re-use of existing cultural heritage data issued by cultural heritage institutions.

Addressing the current needs includes:

- a. generating truly linked open data
- b. balancing openness⁴¹ with the protection of scientific information,
- c. commercialisation and IPR
- d. questions of data management and preservation that will determine how a strategy will be developed within the E-RIHS DIGILAB working group

Cultural Heritage data should be shared under an open license whenever possible, taking into account existing copyright and any restrictions due to national legislation and privacy issues. E-RIHS, in accordance with international standards, frameworks and interoperability protocols will take the necessary steps and precautions to guarantee open access, sharing data and make research results useful and accessible to the public.

3. Heritage Science leads to innovation and exploitation

The importance of IPR in innovation has been documented well both within the research and in the industrial fields. According to O. Granstrand⁴², “the use of property-like rights to induce innovations of various kinds is perhaps the oldest institutional arrangement that is particular to innovation as a social phenomenon” and global innovation entered in a “pro-patent or pro-IP era” since the last quarter of the past century.

As highlighted in the E-RIHS Analysis of Innovation Background, D9.2⁴³, E-RIHS has a strong potential as an innovation ecosystem because of the multi-disciplinary nature of the scientific fields it covers

and because it brings together a large pool of expertise and facilities. The facilitation of exchanges between the stakeholders and common smart specialisation strategy and joint research activities could make E-RIHS one of the lead innovators in Heritage Science globally. Although the current rate of E-RIHS PP members engaging with the industry with the specific purpose of transforming their developments into market ready products is relatively low (20%), the potential for exploitation of E-RIHS results is remains strong through cultural industries at large (museum exhibitions, tourism, etc.) and through collaboration with other Research and Development public or private stakeholders.

In order to create and sustain such an innovation and exploitation ecosystem, E-RIHS will build on its distributed nature to make the best use of local and national Technology Transfer Offices (TTO). National Nodes will create an opportunity from TTOs from several national institutions to harmonise their practices in the field of Heritage Science and to devise a comprehensive IPR strategy regarding their E-RIHS activity. The added value of the ERIC will be to collect information, to elaborate a European innovation and exploitation strategy together with its members, to promote best practices in its ecosystem and to make sure that its commercial activities stay within the limits of the ERIC regulation.

III. E-RIHS ERIC: a distributed RI that generates and protects intellectual work

E-RIHS will be a distributed research infrastructure organised around a Central Hub and a network of national nodes. The distribution of competences and the legal organisation of the infrastructure is of a paramount importance for the establishment of an IPR strategy that is reasonable in terms of work distribution while providing a satisfactory degree of IPR protection in an Open Science framework.

1. A distributed structure for optimal national and international protection

As highlighted in several deliverables in WP4 as well as in WPs 2 and 3, the term “E-RIHS” refers to the complete infrastructure, i.e. the ERIC and the infrastructures that are in some way legally connected to the ERIC⁴⁴. This system of legal connections between the members of the infrastructure is not specific to E-RIHS and is actually common in European distributed research infrastructures (ERICs). Three main levels of activities are relevant for IPR management and IPR policy purposes:

- **ERIC level:** it is composed of the Central Hub, the General Assembly, the Committee of National Nodes and the Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board. The ERIC has its own legal personality and is governed by EU law, the law of the host country, and its statutes⁴⁵.
- **National Node level:** each National Node corresponds to a Member of the ERIC. They integrate the national participating facilities or institutions. Some Nodes will have a legal personality under their national law, some will not.
- **Facilities level:** individual facilities or institutions with their own legal personalities. Some have their own legal personality, some are attached to a bigger umbrella organisation (national research organisation, state authority, university, etc.)

It is evident from this system that in order to devise a comprehensive strategy for E-RIHS IPR management, two main types of activities need to be considered: a) activities performed by the ERIC itself (central activities), and b) activities performed on behalf of the ERIC or under the E-RIHS label.

A. Central activities

The central activities are performed by staff hired by the E-RIHS ERIC or seconded personnel provided by its members. This means that their relation to the ERIC will be defined in an employment contract or a secondment agreement. These contracts and agreements will have an appropriate clause on IPR that describes the rules that apply to their work. We expect E-RIHS ERIC to adopt in there the standard clause according to which:

- All the work of an individual under the contractual relation belongs to the ERIC.
- The ERIC owns all results when they are produced by the central hub, whether they can be subjected to IPR or not. It owns IPR related revenues.
- The ERIC can only decide if it will pursue IPR protection or not. It is responsible for the cost of protecting those rights.
- The ERIC will duly acknowledge authorship of the work, except if the author explicitly wishes not to be acknowledged.

As per the E-RIHS Business plan⁴⁶, the Central Hub provides the coordination of the infrastructure as a whole. In practical terms and with a focus on IPR issues, it means:

- Providing a central access point to the four access platforms according to the E-RIHS access policy and its procedures⁴⁷. In terms of IPR, it involves building and running the E-RIHS catalogue, where entries will be validated by the rights holders. All scientific results will not be handled by the ERIC itself but by the providers through their National Nodes.
- Operating DIGILAB. At this stage of development of the DIGILAB platform (its exact functioning is still under discussion in the E-RIHS DIGILAB Working group), it is hard to exactly identify the IPR risks associated with DIGILAB. According to the ongoing work on the topic, it appears that the E-RIHS ERIC will share the ownership of DIGILAB with some of its members and that most of the data and the services will be provided under a creative commons licence.
- All the other central activities (promotion and development of good practices, protocols, and standards, International liaisons towards the global E-RIHS, supporting the E-RIHS Academy, and administrative activities) do not pose a significant challenge in identifying and protecting IPR rights.

B. National protection, European and international co-creation

A significant part of the scientific activity of E-RIHS will be performed by the Members on behalf of the E-RIHS ERIC through their National Nodes. Although there are some cases in which activities could be performed by several National Nodes at the same period of times, we expect the majority of E-RIHS activities to be performed in a single country. This means that, apart from some transnational activities, it will be reasonably straightforward to identify which national jurisdiction applies to an activity and any exploitable or non-exploitable results.

The statutes of E-RIHS grant a deal of flexibility in terms of structuring the national nodes. This will translate in a great heterogeneity of legal statuses between the National Nodes. The most advanced and integrated Nodes will have their own legal personality. In that case, it could potentially be the owner of some IPR related to E-RIHS activities performed in their territory. In other cases, nodes will be formed around an agreement between national parties. It is unlikely that this kind of agreement impacts the way the members of a national node deal with their own IPR. Finally, some national nodes will be formed using the legal personality of one prominent national organisation (sometimes called an “umbrella organisation”), in which case other partners will have to adopt an agreement on the distribution of IPR between the members of the national node. Regardless of their choice,

national nodes will have to assume the burden of IPR protection of E-RIHS activities that were performed under their supervision.

Activities conducted at the national level involving potential IPR include:

- Supplying access to partner facilities
- Organising scientific outreach and training activities,
- Overseeing the in-kind contribution to the ERIC

The provision of access is probably the most complex issue E-RIHS will have to face IPR-wise, but it is expected to be able to build upon years of practice thanks to the IPERION HS project and previous integrated projects (IPERION CH and CHARISMA). IPERION HS indeed provides an important opportunity to test out the implementation of the E-RIHS access policy. In particular, it will strengthen the consortium's data policy and it might bring to light some IPR related issues the members of the consortium did not yet encounter in 20 years of providing transnational access through European projects.

All the results obtained through an E-RIHS access will be automatically owned by the authors (i.e. the users). In most cases, the providers will have a joint ownership over these results in accordance with their national or local rules. The E-RIHS will not own the results. Notwithstanding exceptional cases when a commercial activity is performed, the access to any E-RIHS service will be conditioned to the adoption of open data solutions such as the most open Creative Commons Licences⁴⁸ or other equally open licenses (Licence Ouverte / Open Licence⁴⁹, Open Government Licence⁵⁰, etc.). In this way, E-RIHS ERIC will automatically be able to reuse the results without having to request the rights in a special agreement.

The regulatory framework on ERICs allows the participation of intergovernmental organisations as members of E-RIHS ERIC. In this case, the obligations related to their membership will be adapted to their international and non-territorial nature. Whether such organisations are members, observers, or partners of E-RIHS, the guiding principle managing IPR should be joint-ownership of results and associated rights between the organisations. When applicable, the burden associated to protecting IPR will be split between the organisations unless otherwise stated in a written agreement (framework agreements or case-by-case agreements if there is no framework agreement).

2. Knowledge circulation and the sharing of “IPR management burden”

As noted in the E-RIHS Innovation Agenda⁵¹, IPR management is a key factor in a successful innovation strategy. Providing an adaptive yet efficient framework that encourages and protects innovation can represent a significant burden, both in financial and in labour terms.

A. The E-RIHS risk management plan applied to IPR

As stated already, deficient IPR management can lead to several types of risk (theft, copyright issues, domain names, disputes, etc.). This is why we will build on the E-RIHS Risk Management Framework⁵² to elaborate a clear recommendation on the repartition of IPR related work within the different E-RIHS levels: the central hub (the ERIC), the National Hubs (the Members), and Individual Member organisations.

As highlighted in III.1, the Central Hub will not be tasked with managing the most critical IPR issues because, with a few exceptions, research and development data will be handled at the national level. This shelters the central hub from corporate risks, but, because access is officially granted by

the E-RIHS ERIC and other activities are conducted under its label, it leaves it vulnerable to reputational risks.

To address this risk, the Central Hub will work on identifying the risks of the infrastructure as a whole and will monitor the National IPR implementation work. This monitoring will be mostly performed by the Committee of National Nodes in their yearly evaluation of the National In-kind contribution. If a problem arises, the Committee will either decide that the risks have no potential impact on E-RIHS as a whole and will let the National Node manage it, or it will decide to escalate the problem to the Director General who will judge if an appropriate measure must be taken at the ERIC level. This decision will be motivated by the impact and the probability of the risk, as well as its transnational relevance.

Because of their mandate, the members of the Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board will also be in position to identify potential IPR vulnerabilities related to the scientific work within E-RIHS. In such a case, they will task the Committee of National Nodes to respond appropriately. This applies to both protection and infringement of IPR. It must be noted that a severe infringement by a National Node or an institution involved in a National Node could constitute a breach of a Member's obligation under the E-RIHS Statutes (as defined in the Rule 17 of the E-RIHS Rules of Procedures⁵³). In this exceptional case, the General Assembly could manage the risk by starting a termination of Membership procedure.

Most of the burden to identify, manage and monitor such issues will thus be borne by the National Nodes of E-RIHS. Apart from the ones that will chose to incorporated under a common infrastructure with its own legal personality, a National Node will replicate this IPR risk management strategy at the national level. The governing bodies overseeing the nodes will play a role of monitoring (and if necessary escalating) IPR risks but will not own or manage them. As for the European level, they could be required to act depending on the potential impact and the probability of the risk, as well as its trans-institutional relevance. In case of National Nodes incorporated under a common legal personality, they will function as a large national institution and risks will automatically become of national relevance. This leaves the local institutions performing the scientific work under the E-RIHS label the main owners and managers of IPR risks, with an obligation to report any risk that could affect the rest of the infrastructure. If we base our observations on the current of former members of the series of projects that lead to E-RIHS, a great majority of institutions involved in E-RIHS will be large institutions with dedicated legal services that include IP lawyers and technology transfer officers. Local coordinators or directors of the institutions will he held accountable for the efficient protection of most of the E-RIHS IPR. In case of institutions with no specific expertise in this field, the National Nodes will have to provide a forum where such institutions could learn from the best national practices.

B. "E-RIHS IPR" in the age of open science

ERICs are required to "contribute to the dissemination and optimisation of the results" and "contribute to the mobility of knowledge and/or research within the ERA"⁵⁴. In order to comply with these obligations and in accordance with its Scientific Strategy, E-RIHS will perform and promote open science and open access to results to the greatest extent possible.

In order to implement open science principles, E-RIHS will set clear requirements in the context of its access policy and also when conducting other scientific and/or training activities. In particular, it will condition the access to its various facilities and platforms to proper acknowledgment of the E-RIHS support and to the use of Creative Commons (CC-BY, CC-BY-SA) licences (or any license that would provide the same degree of openness). As stated earlier, the ERIC would not own the data produced by its users but with this framework it maintains the right to reuse it. Although it is unlikely

that the Central Hub and the Access providers will be able to check if all the data produced under the E-RIHS Label are made available after an embargo period, they will easily monitor if the access report and its preliminary results are uploaded to open platforms. The IPR related to potential commercial activities by E-RIHS ERIC or under its label will be described on a case-by-case basis in service contracts.

Because the DIGILAB Implementation Plan is still being discussed within the international DIGILAB Working Group, it is hard to determine the exact repartition of IPR between the ERIC, its members and third parties (either other institutional partners or private companies), but its data policy should follow the FAIR principles. DIGILAB will be a distributed digital platform across Europe (and beyond). The attribution of background rights will largely depend on the implementation strategy adopted by the consortium, but the ERIC will most likely have a co-ownership with its members, who will be in charge of most of the IPR burden. The actual design of the DIGILAB virtual research environment and how it would enrich the data will be a key factor in the attribution of foreground IPR. This choice will have to be made within the financial framework decided by the interim General Assembly and will also be based on European and National opportunities.

Conclusion

Intellectual Property Rights are a key enabling concept for the pursuit of E-RIHS objectives: the co-creation of knowledge on tangible Heritage and the integration of the Heritage Science community around open science practices. After identifying the different kinds of IPR categories that could apply to both the administrative and the scientific work of the whole Research Infrastructure, we showed that the international nature of E-RIHS, together with other risks, make the IPR management complex and multi-levelled. As defined by the consortium, “Heritage science is the interdisciplinary domain of scientific study of heritage”. This implies that our work is focused on material objects with special (sometimes disputed) ownership rules. This is why E-RIHS will be careful to avoid all the questions pertaining to ownership disputes and dedicate its work to creating scientific data on Heritage and encouraging associated innovation and exploitation processes. In order to reach an optimal repartition of IPR and the associated protection burden, E-RIHS will build on its decentralised nature to use the pre-existing resources and its members when it comes to scientific results with an appropriate licensing scheme to allow the free circulation of knowledge within the ERA and beyond. E-RIHS ERIC itself will have limited IPR protection costs and exclusive rights, but it will oversee and monitor the good implementation of its policy through its different bodies to ensure that its objectives are reached. Although it does not own the heritage objects themselves, E-RIHS will be able to share the scientific benefit of its work through a system of open licensing with the Heritage Science community at large.

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